

TRANSNATURE

Policy Recommendations: Julian Alps

Funding Opportunities

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Date: September 2025

This research was funded by **Biodiversa+**, the European Biodiversity Partnership, in the context of the **TRANSNATURE project** under the 2021-2022 **BiodivProtect** joint call. It was co-funded by the **European Commission (GA No. 101052342)** and with the following funding organisations: **the Autonomous Province of Bolzano-Bozen - South Tyrol**, **the Research Council of Finland**, **the Agencia Estatal de Investigación**, and **the Research Foundation Flanders**.

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Introduction

This report presents a series of policy recommendations designed to address the urgent need for innovative funding solutions for nature conservation in the Julian Alps. Facing persistent budgetary limitations, local stakeholders have called for new approaches to secure financial resources in interviews and focus groups. Some recommendations refer to optimizing existing instruments, others to exploring untested mechanisms. The methodology combines an analysis of current funding models as declared by the local stakeholders involved in the participatory process with the identification of emerging opportunities from national and international practice, engaging local partners and relevant authorities to ensure practical applicability. Some recommendations focus on streamlining and strengthening established funding channels, while others propose forward-thinking strategies that demand coordinated institutional action and enhanced collaboration among key stakeholders.

The recommendations included in this report are ranked according to their evaluated feasibility, scalability, and additionality,¹ This ranking was determined by analyzing feedback collected from interviews and focus groups conducted at the pilot site, ensuring that local perspectives and experiences informed the evaluation. In addition, a qualitative assessment was carried out to consider the institutional complexities linked to each proposed intervention. While Recommendations 6 and 7 present higher levels of challenge due to their complexity, they are also recognized as the most innovative approaches among those considered in this analysis.

¹ Feasibility indicates how realistic and practical it is to implement this recommendation locally in the short run (from very easy to nearly impossible). Scalability indicates how easily this solution could work across the entire region (or even beyond) ranging from specific to easily transferable measures. Additionality indicates how much extra benefit a measure creates that wouldn't happen anyway ranging from business as usual to major new impacts.

Policy Recommendation 1

Leveraging UNESCO MAB Certification to Maximise Access to National and EU Funds

Main problem:

MAB biosphere status is under-utilised when municipalities and parks bid for national and EU funds that are increasingly financed through tourism-derived revenues (e.g., Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) “Villages” call, Slovenian Recovery and Resilience Plan/*Slovenski načrt za okrevanje in odpornost*, both aligned with the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility). Low awareness and fragmented applications reduce success rates in accessing the mentioned funds, for which the MAB label already provides a competitive advantage.

Addressees:

Park authorities (PNPG & TNP); Italian Ministry for Ecological Transition (MASE); Slovenian Ministry of Environment (MOPE); Regional Development Agencies; Regional Tourism Boards.

Recommendation:

Establishing a “MAB Certification Gateway” unit that bundles small-scale projects into MAB-compliant proposals and provides ready-to-submit project dossiers, aligned with national programmes, that already contain pre-filled strategic-fit justification quoting the MAB zonation map and a signed letter of endorsement template from the MAB Secretariat for local proponents, especially municipalities.

The UNESCO MAB label improves competitive scoring, yet stakeholders “often do not know how to use it”. The Gateway unit—hosted within the MAB Secretariat and possibly coordinated by a seconded officer from regional (IT)/national (SI) public administrations—will:

- Map upcoming calls (NRRP, PRR, Recovery and Resilience Plans) and pre-validate projects for MAB compliance.
- Supply already available information on the UNESCO MAB JATBR area (e.g., zoning maps, biodiversity indices, visitor-flow data) to cut preparation time by 50%.
- Offer a fast-track endorsement letter proving the project’s strategic value, a crucial step since the certification “indirectly facilitates access to funding”.

Added value: Converts symbolic MAB status into a practical multiplier for accessing existing public funds, representing a “quick win” due to its high feasibility and balanced impact.

Policy Recommendation 2

Piloting Carbon Credits for Forest Conservation under EU 2023 Guidance

Main problem:

Forest-rich municipalities cannot monetise carbon sequestration because fragmented national rules, lack of scalable models, and low private-sector engagement deter credit issuance.

Addressees:

Park authorities (project developers); Italian MASE and Slovenian MOPE; voluntary carbon buyers (tourism operators, energy firms).

Recommendation:

Issuing ex-post carbon credits strictly for above-ground forest conservation, registered under the EU voluntary market standard and marketed to tourism operators seeking net-zero pledges, as a transboundary pilot project. This additional revenue would therefore be funded partly by tourism's carbon footprint.

This is considered as a major project in terms of impact and additionality, but showing a lower feasibility. This combination directly supports a pilot approach. As a new mechanism, its introduction needs to be supported by public consultation or in accordance with local operators (e.g., during the European Charter on Sustainable Tourism – ECST– Annual Forum) to explore the availability of local tourist operators.

Following the July 2023 [Guidance on the development of public and private payment schemes for forest ecosystem services](#), the pilot will:

- Delineate 2,000 ha of old-growth and secondary forests inside the MAB reserve, using remote sensing and field plots to quantify t CO₂-e above baseline (defined as per EU 2023 guidance).
- Use the MAB Secretariat as the certifying body, enhancing credibility with buyers marketing credits (€25–40 /t CO₂-e) to tourism operators (**see Rec. 3**) and energy firms.
- Channel revenues (€25–40 /t CO₂-e) into a dedicated Conservation Fund (**Rec. 4**) to guarantee permanence.

Expected first tranche: 25,000 t over five years, generating €0.6–1 million for long-term habitat management.

Added value: Links local forest stewardship to global climate finance, unlocking the highest-potential new revenue stream identified in the analysis; internalizes tourism externalities.

Policy Recommendation 3

Piloting PES Contracts for Tourism Operators (Lodges, Ski Lifts, Guides)

Main problem:

Tourism operators, as direct beneficiaries of high-quality ecosystems, are an untapped source of private funding for conservation via Payment for Ecosystem Service (PES) schemes, which currently lack operational frameworks.

Addressees:

Regional tourism associations; local tourism operators; Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (JATBR) Coordination Committee; MASE and MOPE (IT and SI).

Recommendation:

Piloting tourism-linked PES contracts embedded into Tourism-Based Conservation Fund (TBCF) regulations (**Rec. 4**): a group of volunteer operators contribute e.g., 0.5% of gross turnover to a pooled fund for visible habitat maintenance (e.g., trail restoration) in exchange for marketing advantages (e.g., "MAB-Certified Green Partner" label) (See also **Rec. 1 on Governance**).

This approach operationalizes the "tourism-government-nature" circle by directly linking private profit to public good.

Contracts would:

- Use blockchain or similar transparent registries for transparent payment tracking.²
- Link contributions to visitor satisfaction metrics (e.g., % of tourists rating biodiversity as a key attraction, measured by a simple survey at strategic tourism touchpoints)³ by reinvesting funds directly into projects that enhance visitor experience, creating a virtuous feedback loop.
- Pilot 50 operators across Bovec (SI) and Tarvisio (IT), targeting €200k/year after a 5 year phased test.⁴

Added value: Aligns private tourism profits with public conservation outcomes, operationalising the "tourism-government-nature" circle and creating a market-based and self-sustaining funding mechanism.

² The blockchain technology is a secure digital ledger system that creates permanent, transparent, and tamper-proof records of transactions. It addresses the risk of misallocation without transparency and provides the streamlined reporting needed to reduce administrative burdens as noted by local stakeholders.

³ A standardized 3-question survey may include questions like:

- 1) "How important was biodiversity/natural scenery to your decision to visit the Julian Alps?" (Answer on a scale: 1 (Not important) to 5 (Deciding factor))
- 2) "Have you noticed visible conservation improvements during your visit?" (answer Yes/No with photo verification option via mobile app)
- 3) "Would you be willing to pay a small premium for verified conservation contributions by tourism businesses?" (Yes/No)

⁴ The test may be run through phases e.g. from businesses already aligned with sustainability values to a tiered-contribution system with clear marketing benefits, to larger operators and integration in the TBCF eco-tax system in **recommendation 4**.

Policy Recommendation 4

Institutionalising a Tourism-Based Conservation Fund (TBCF) via Statutory Eco-Tax

Main problem:

Permanent governmental funds for biodiversity are almost absent. Tourism, the sector with the highest impact, does not systematically contribute to conservation, making funding unpredictable.

Addressees:

Regional and Local Governments (Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Slovenian Municipalities); Alpine Tourist Boards; Ministry of Finance (IT/SI).

Recommendation:

Enacting a mandatory overnight eco-tax (€1–€3/night) earmarked for a transboundary Tourism-Based Conservation Fund (TBCF), legally ring-fenced for conservation goals.⁵ The measure shows a low level of feasibility due to the political commitment required in the area for its implementation.

Stakeholders explicitly demand governmental funds from tourism development and to set up a circle of tourism, government, and nature protection. Given the political sensitivity of introducing new taxes, it is advised to organize public awareness campaigns and consultation rounds with local tourism associations and tourism operators.

The locally competent authorities would:

1. Legislate the tax under regional/local tourism acts, with periodical reviews every 5 years to ensure public acceptance. The competence on this matter is up to regional governments in Italy and to municipalities operating within national tax frameworks requiring Ministry of Finance coordination in Slovenia.
2. Distribute e.g., 70 % to core-area conservation (e.g., wolf-livestock conflict prevention), 20% to behavioural-change campaigns (**Rec. 5**), and 10% to administrative costs, in consultation with TBCF.
3. Govern via a joint IT-SI board chaired by the JATBR Secretariat, ensuring transparent annual reporting to tourism operators and municipalities.

Precedents: Trentino's "Provincial Law 11/2019" earmarks €0.50/night for alpine biodiversity, raising €4.2 million/year. This case demonstrates that earmarking funds is legally viable and can generate substantial revenue (€4.2 million/year). Scaling this model across the Julian Alps (4 million overnight stays/year) could secure **€4–12 million annually**, replacing 25–60 % of current project-based gaps.

Added value: Converts tourism externalities into predictable public funds, providing the stable, long-term budget required for effective conservation and aligning visitor contributions with ecological stewardship.

⁵ Specific goals may be selected depending on local priorities or preferences.

Policy Recommendation 5

Introducing Behavioural-Change Grants Scheme for Local Stewardship

Main problem:

Assigning conservation responsibilities to residents/farmers without dedicated funds undermines compliance and trust, creating bottlenecks that lower the feasibility of many conservation projects.

Addressees:

The JATBR Coordination Committee; the EU Just Transition Fund (managed by Ministry of Finance in SI); the regional government (Giunta Regionale) of Friuli Venezia-Giulia; national governments; IT MASE; SI municipalities (authorized by the national government) and Municipality of Bovec (lead implementing municipality); SI Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (MKGP); Slovenian Forest Service; EU DG Environment and DG Agriculture.

Recommendation:

Creating a €2 million multi-annual micro-grant scheme (€5k–€20k/project), funded through: (1) 10% allocation from the Tourism-Based Conservation Fund (TBCF) revenue stream, (2) matching contribution from the EU Just Transition Fund channeled through national implementation frameworks, and (3) complementary regional funds from Friuli-Venezia Giulia's Rural Development Programme and Slovenia's Agricultural Support Scheme (regional and project-based funds).

This fund intended for behavioural-change initiatives, co-designed with local actors and administered via the Tourism-Based Conservation Fund (TBCF) (see **Rec. 4**). The scheme is administered through a dedicated Grants Committee operating under the TBCF Governing Board, with technical oversight from Parco Naturale Prealpi Giulie (PNPG, IT) and Triglav National Park Authority (TNP, SI), ensuring compliance with national funding regulations in both countries. Stakeholders stressed how if you assign people responsibility, you need funds dedicated to that. Administered via the TBCF (Rec. 4) and co-financed by the EU Just Transition Fund, the scheme ensures accountability through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): % reduction in predator complaints, hectares under stewardship contracts, youth engagement rates.

Grants would target:

- Farmers' training in predator-friendly practices (electric fences, herd dogs) (see **rec. 4 on Governance**).
- School programmes linking tourism revenues to citizen science results and data collection (e.g., monitoring alpine flora via apps).
- NGO-led campaigns reducing human-wildlife conflict through participatory theatre on coexistence, and multilingual signage for hikers.

Added value: Transforms regulatory obligations into community-owned actions, increases local buy-in, trust in institutions and the overall feasibility of the entire conservation strategy.

Policy Recommendation 6

Establishing a Transboundary Endowment Fund for Long-Term Financial Resilience

Main problem:

Project-based funding and even tourism-derived revenues are pro-cyclical and vulnerable to extreme shocks (pandemics, economic crises) and consistent political will over legislatures, threatening the continuity of multi-annual conservation programs (e.g., wolf-livestock coexistence measures). Current funding covers only 40-50% of conservation needs, creating critical gaps during revenue shortfalls.

Addressees:

IT Friuli-Venezia Giulia Regional Government (Department for Environment); IT MASE; PNPG; IT Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP); SI Ministry of Finance; MOPE); Development Bank of Slovenia (SID); TNP; Seed Donors—EU LIFE/Horizon Europe; EIB Green Finance; private philanthropies.

Recommendation:

Establish a phased conservation reserve mechanism (fund) that provides counter-cyclical financing during revenue shortfalls, starting with a pilot reserve fund and transitioning to a fully structured endowment. Implementation can take place by phase, e.g.:

- Pilot Phase (Years 1-2): create a conservation reserve fund within existing regional budgets that accumulates surplus Tourism-Based Conservation Fund (TBCF) revenues during high-tourism years, with legally permissible annual rollover provisions.
- Transition Phase (Years 3-4): structure a blended finance vehicle through CDP (Italy) and SID (Slovenia) combining green bond proceeds with philanthropic contributions.
- Mature Phase (Year 5+): transition to a fully structured endowment with e.g., annual 4% disbursement (€2M/year) to top up the TBCF when annual receipts fall below e.g., €3 million.

This back-stop mechanism guarantees continuity without contradicting the tourism-first revenue strategy. The verification of the efficacy of the mechanism is performed through:

- a transparent registry showing specific conservation outcomes funded during shortfalls, disclosing funding sources (using blockchain technology),
- annual independent verification against conservation continuity metrics,
- public dashboard tracking fund performance and conservation impact.

Precedents: National environmental endowments (e.g., in Bulgaria and Romania, originally seeded with international funds) and university endowments (e.g., Harvard, Yale) provide well-established governance and investment models for managing such funds. In the field of nature conservation precedents include the Carpathian Conservation Endowment Fund (CCEF), the Austrian Alpine Conservation Endowment (AACE), the Danube River Protection Endowment Fund, and the Bulgarian Biodiversity Preservation Endowment Fund (BBPEF).

The BBPEF (1998) was initially seeded by the Global Environment Facility (GEF) support, then nationally managed. With an initial endowment of \$3 million (GEF grant), it reached \$15.2 million (2023). It provides an annual disbursement rate of 4-5% (\$608,000-\$760,000), with verification costs of 0.3% of annual proceeds (\$1,824-\$2,280). The Fund has a diversified investment strategy (60% fixed income, 30% equities, 10% alternative assets). Over 25 years, it supported 32 conservation projects annually and covered 70% of operational costs for protected areas. It maintained 100% project continuity during the 2008-2009 financial crisis and achieved 12-17% ROI on nature-based conservation projects.

Added value: Insulates core conservation budgets from political and economic cycles while respecting national fiscal constraints, guaranteeing financial sustainability and permanence for the most critical conservation actions aligned with public finance law in Italy and Slovenia.

Policy Recommendation 7

Creating a Pooled Green-Bond Issuance Facility

Main problem:

Individual municipalities (<5,000 inhabitants) cannot access the €150 bn EU green-bond market due to high fixed / issuance costs, lack of technical expertise, and project pipelines that are too small to attract institutional investors, limiting their ability to finance transformative conservation infrastructure.

Addressees:

Municipalities within the JATBR (territorial beneficiaries); IT Friuli-Venezia Giulia Regional Government; Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP); PNPG; Ministries of Finance; Development Bank of Slovenia (SID); TNP; Slovenian Association of Municipalities; European Investment Bank (EIB); Green Finance Advisory.

Recommendation:

Launching in Italy and Slovenia a pooled green-bond initiative with National and regional institutions partnering with an established national promotional bank (e.g., Cassa Depositi e Prestiti - CDP in Italy) or a specialised green finance aggregator.

A special green bond facility including technical and financial expertise will pre-screen and bundle local projects (forest lowland restoration, riverbank rewilding, sustainable tourism infrastructure, **see Rec. 1 on Governance**) against EU Taxonomy criteria to create a credible investment pipeline, operating through a legally viable structure. The green bond facility will aggregate biodiversity projects from municipalities and parks into a sufficiently large and investment-grade ticket size to access the capital markets efficiently and at lower cost, working within existing legal constraints of both countries. The facility acts as a financial aggregator and de-risking agent, and should provide credit enhancement (e.g., first-loss guarantees) to lower the risk for investors, with a realistic repayment structure to be further framed. The initiative can be technically led by the partner institution (e.g., CDP, SID), which will provide the financial structuring, credit assessment, and market access. The role of the Parks and Regions is to select and prepare the pipeline of bankable conservation projects.

The proceeds from the operation will be used for:

- financing the project pipeline so to achieve measurable goals (impact bond logic),
- capitalizing the principal of the endowment conservation fund as a long run objective, whose annual dividends are used to finance activities.

Depending on the Parks' management priorities and considerations, a variable share of the proceeds from the operation (e.g., 20%) can be earmarked as seed capital for the **Recommendation 6 Endowment Fund**, creating a direct link between local "pro-biodiversity investment" and long-term resilience.

Currently, Friuli-Venezia Giulia's regional government hasn't any regional agency with bond-issuing capacity, however Sviluppo FVG could support "blended finance" instruments by

providing e.g., grants to reduce the risk of a financed project. In Slovenia, the Development Bank of Slovenia (SID) is the authorized issuer of public bonds under national banking regulations.

The European Investment Bank (EIB) can act as an advisor providing green finance expertise. In case of issuance of 10-year notes under a unified "Julian Alps Sustainable Bond Framework" aligned with ICMA Green Bond Principles, the repayment scheme could develop as follows:

- an initial "grace period" (up to 2 years) with interest-only payments covered by EU transition funds and public grants,
- a "progressive principal repayment" (e.g. since year 3) from tourism infrastructure revenues (e.g., 5% annually),
- "increased repayment rates" as conservation benefits emerge (e.g. 10% annually in Years 6-8 from TBCF allocations),
- "full repayment" by Year 10, through diversified revenue streams from financed local projects (e.g., a share of carbon credit revenues).

Verification of the projects and across phases is performed through a Joint Technical Committee of the PNPG (IT) and the TNP (SI). Local implementation is supervised by municipalities within the JATBR providing project pipelines.

Precedents: Pooled bond issuance facilities are a common tool for municipal finance in countries like the Netherlands and for sectors like social housing, proving the model's effectiveness in achieving economies of scale.

Water Authority Friesland (Wetterskip Fryslân) Green Bond is a case with a sub-sovereign public entity (a regional water authority) issuing a bond for environmental purposes (raised proceeds for €150 million): funds were exclusively allocated to projects aligned with the EU Green Bond Standard and the Dutch Green Bond Guidelines.

Republic of France Sovereign Green Bond (OAT Vert) (2017) is a sovereign issuance characterized by transparency and detailed allocation to biodiversity and conservation, involving a national government. Proceeds have also been used for funding national parks, Natura 2000 sites, and the restoration of degraded ecosystems.

Primary investor categories likely to buy green bonds may include e.g., European ESG-Focused Institutional Investors (aimed at meeting EU Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) requirements), Impact Investors Specializing in Nature Finance (seeking 7-9% blended financial/environmental returns), and Local Financial Institutions (supporting regional development while meeting ESG commitments).

Added value: Unlocks capital-market finance for small actors at a lower cost, reducing legal and marketing costs for the involved municipalities and other local/regional stakeholders (likely 70–90 basis-point cost saving versus individual issues), enabling transformative, large-scale conservation projects while creating an opportunity to capitalize the region's permanent endowment.

List of abbreviations

ECST	European Charter for Sustainable Tourism
IT	Italy or Italian
JATBR	Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (MAB UNESCO)
MAB	Man and Biosphere
MASE	Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security
MOPE	Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Energy
PES	Payment for Ecosystem Service
PNPG	Natural Park Prealpi Giulie
SI	Slovenia or Slovenian
TNP	Triglav National Park
UNESCO	The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization